

**BANK LOAN OFFICERS' PERCEPTIONS OF CORPORATE FINANCIAL DISCLOSURE IN THE
BANKING SECTOR OF BANGLADESH: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS**

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ABSTRACT

Entire financial disclosure i. e., mandatory disclosure and voluntary disclosure are both included in an effective information disclosure system. Mandatory disclosure is the basic demand of the market, and voluntary disclosure is the extended demand of the market, because of its informative complement to the timing, content and depth of disclosure. Some specific disclosure includes the laws governing the formations of banks; the by-laws established by the bank itself, and the structure of the bank. The issue of the corporate financial disclosure is receiving greater attention both the developed and developing countries in the corporate sectors particularly. Nevertheless, this issue still remains largely unfamiliar in the corporate arena of the banking sector of Bangladesh. This study focuses on the practices of some selected disclosure practicing through annual reports by banks operating in Bangladesh. For this paper, an empirical study as well as a questionnaire survey has been conducted. The principal findings include, firstly, most of the banks discloses the name of default directors with amount due, the name of borrower directors, prepares aging schedule, fixes the rate of provisions for bad debts, do not take qualified opinion or disclaimer, creates secret reserves in the balance-sheet and uses cost principle in valuing assets and secondly the respondents are in favor of such disclosures. As it is requirement, the current disclosures are not ample in evaluating the goals of corporate financial disclosure in the banking sector.

INTRODUCTION

The aim of the present research is to enhance our understanding of the corporate financial reporting disclosure environment in Bangladesh by seeking the opinions of the Bank Loan Officers that are expected to be affected by such an environment. Our objective therefore is to discover the major corporate information sources to the major interested parties in the banking sector in Bangladesh. Such a study will also shed light on how corporate financial disclosure preparers and regulators can improve the current corporate reporting practices as well as provide rich description of some aspects of financial accounting and its environment in Bangladesh. Although the subject of the present research is not a new one, it is, however, handled more thoroughly and has a broader scope than previous research attempts. There is a paucity of research regarding users information needs in developing countries. There are the studies of Wallace (1988a, 1988b) in Nigeria and Nicholls and Ahmed (1995) in Bangladesh, which measured the quality of disclosure taking into consideration the perception of users in a developing country perspective. This chapter analyzes the results of the questionnaire survey among a sample of bank loan officers. The main trust of this paper is to focus the perception of the users (BLO) about their perceived importance for various sources of information in making their decisions, reasons for using financial information, and their opinions regarding the adequacy and reliability of information of annual reports. Different users groups have different objectives in using financial reports and it has been pointed out that they may have diverse informational needs (Benjamin and Stanga, 1977; p. 187).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The destination of this study is to focus the perception of the BLO as users about their perceived importance for various sources of information in making their decisions, and their opinions regarding the adequacy and reliability of voluntary information of annual reports. This study attempts to focus on the present scenario of corporate financial disclosure by the banks of Bangladesh in their annual reports. Objectives of this study cover the followings:

- (a) Evaluation of guidelines for standard corporate financial voluntary disclosure.
- (b) Analyzing the corporate voluntary disclosure practice in Bangladesh by the banking companies through the empirical analysis.
- (c) To know BLOs' attitude towards this type of voluntary disclosure.
- (d) To find out the adequacy of corporate financial disclosure on a voluntary basis.
- (e) Recommending some measures to take a sound corporate financial report by the banking companies.

METHODOLOGY

The article is based on empirical study as well as questionnaire survey i. e. primary information. For the purpose of the study, the questionnaires were sent to 20 bank loan officers (BLO) of different banks. Among them 17 respondents gave valuable feedback regarding the questionnaire while others were reluctant to give any information regarding this.

QUESTIONS SOLICITED

The questionnaire for the current study was pre-tested with personnel of accounting department, prominent academicians, and researchers. The respondents were again supplied with the questionnaire two weeks after they filled up first questionnaire. The final questionnaire for the study contained a covering letter and a brief background of the study. In the covering letter, it was mentioned that the researcher was conducting the study as part of PhD thesis, so that the respondents would understand that the study is sponsored which might increase changes of better responses. Identifying the perceptions of various bank loan officers about the disclosure of the selected items of voluntary information in the banks annual reports through a questionnaire survey constitutes the main part of the study. The first part of the final version of questionnaire included questions representing the name, occupation, age, accounting training, educational qualifications of the respondents and the second part contained voluntary disclosure information of the banks stated earlier. The questionnaire used in the survey is presented in Appendix. To make this paper more informative different published textbooks, related journals, reports, seminar papers and research works have been analyzed. The questionnaire survey method, regardless of its inherent drawbacks seemed appropriate for this type of study. Survey method is most appropriate and effective for drawing conclusion regarding peoples' inference and attitudes (Carmichale and Swieringa, 1968). The response rate of the survey among the respondents is discussed in the empirical part of the paper.

RESPONSE RATE

The questionnaire survey consists of a sample of 20 bank loan officers as indicated in Table-1.

Table 1: Response Rate of the Questionnaire Survey

User Group	Sample Size	No. of Responses	Rate of Response (%)
Bank Loan Officers	20	17	85

Table 1 showed the specified user group of the respondents and the size of the sample of the respondents. It also describes the response rate of the questionnaire survey from bank loan officer. Questionnaires were sent to 20 BLOs of the scheduled banks of Bangladesh. The respondents were requested to reply as early as possible for a significant involvement in the study. All the respondents were sent reminders through mobile about 10 days after the questionnaire were sent. Within two weeks of sending, 17 responses were received. The 17 usable responses constituted a response rate of 85 percent, which is acceptable. The response rate is above the rate mentioned by Moser and Kalton (1971) and Ali, Khan Fatima and Masud (2008) as being sufficient for a study leading to policymaking.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

It is widely accepted that corporate annual reports are prepared primarily for external users. Therefore, such reports should be designed, in form and content, according to the needs of the external users (Radebough, and Gray, 1993). These users should be contacted frequently to assess their perceptions about various aspects of the reporting practices of public companies since their views will provide the main feedback to improve the communication function of corporate reports (Epstein, 1993).

One of the pioneering studies to have attempted to discover the information needs and sources of such information was undertaken in the United States by Baker and Haslem in 1973. The authors found that the majority of the individual investors rely heavily on stockbroker's advice as their main source of information about companies. Financial statements, however, were found to be a source of information by only a minority (i.e., 8 per cent) of individual investors. Regarding other information items that are expected to be disclosed by companies, Baker and Haslern (1973) highlight that individual investors attach a great deal of importance to the information about the future expectations of the company. At the same time, individual investors attached a much lower degree of importance to information regarding dividends.

Anderson (1981) also recognized the need for research in this area and focused on institutional investors in Australia. He sought, primarily, to discover their perceptions about the importance of annual corporate reports to their decision making process by analyzing the responses of 188 institutional investors. Anderson (1981) found that Australian investors relied mostly on the annual report when making their investment decisions followed by visits to the companies. Regarding the annual corporate report itself, the most readable sections of the annual report were the balance sheet, profit and loss account, notes to the accounts, and the chairman's statement respectively, The profit and loss account, however, was perceived to be more important than the balance sheet. However, the author failed to perform any statistical test to determine whether there is a significant difference between the users' usage of the annual report sections on the one hand and the perceived importance of such sections on the other hand. Anderson (1981) also documents the external users' desire (i.e., 72 per cent) for additional information to be provided in the annual corporate report such as information about the company's product, current value of long-term assets, and remuneration of directors, Anderson and Epstein (1995) further extended their research by providing a useful investigation on Australia. Unlike the Anderson (1981) study, which specifically focused on Australian institutional investors, the Anderson and Epstein (1995) study was more concerned with individual investors' usage of annual corporate reports. Their findings revealed that the annual corporate reports came third, after stockbrokers* advice and financial newspapers and magazines, as a basis for investment decision of Australian individual investors. Nevertheless, the vast majority of their respondents (i.e., 72 per cent) perceived annual corporate reports to be of only moderate use. Regarding the use of the annual report, the authors highlight the directors' report to be the most thoroughly read followed by the income statement. Nevertheless, their respondents did perceive the income statement to be more useful than the directors' report in making an investment decision. Arguably, Anderson and Epstein (1995) did not statistically determine whether the difference between the pattern of readership of the annual reports' sections and the perceived usefulness of such sections is of any significance in the Australian environment. Respondents had also expressed a desire for the simplification and more explanation of the balance sheet, statement of cash flow, and the income statement. Finally, the authors highlight the Australian investors' demand for additional disclosure in the annual reports; such as pending litigation, unasserted claims, management audit, and information on change of auditor.